

CHIZIQLI TENGLAMALAR SISTEMASI YECHIMINI C++ DASTURI YORDAMIDA KRAMER USULIDA TOPIISH

Butaboyeva Durdon Olimjon qizi

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15104381>

Ma'lumki, kramer usuli (yoki Cramer's rule) - determinantlar yordamida chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini yechish usuli bo'lib, kvadrat matritsaga ega bo'lgan sistemalar uchun qo'llaniladi. Bu usul har bir noma'lumning qiymatini topish uchun asosiy matritsaning determinantlari bilan ishlaydi. Asosan 2x2, 3x3 kabi kichik o'lchamli tenglamalar sistemalarida samarali bo'ladi.

Kramer usuli odatda determinantlar usuli ham deb ataladi. Bu usulning algoritmi quyidagicha. Dastlab quyidagi (n+1) ta n - tartibli

$$\Delta = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} \quad \Delta_{x_1} = \begin{vmatrix} b_1 & a_{12} & \dots & a_{1n} \\ b_2 & a_{22} & \dots & a_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ b_n & a_{n2} & \dots & a_{nn} \end{vmatrix} \quad \dots \quad \Delta_{x_n} = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & a_{12} & \dots & b_1 \\ a_{21} & a_{22} & \dots & b_2 \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ a_{n1} & a_{n2} & \dots & b_n \end{vmatrix}$$

$$x_1 = \frac{\Delta_{x_1}}{\Delta}, \quad x_2 = \frac{\Delta_{x_2}}{\Delta}, \quad \dots,$$

determinantlarning qiymatlari hisoblanadi va no'malumlar

$$x_n = \frac{\Delta_{x_n}}{\Delta}$$

formular yordamida topiladi [5].

Chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini yechimini Oddiy iteratsiya usulida topish

$$\begin{cases} a_{11}x_1 + a_{12}x_2 + \dots + a_{1n}x_n = b_1 \\ a_{21}x_1 + a_{22}x_2 + \dots + a_{2n}x_n = b_2 \\ \dots \\ a_{m1}x_1 + a_{m2}x_2 + \dots + a_{mn}x_n = b_m \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

(1) tenglamalar tizimi almashtirishlar va belgilashlar natijasida quyidagi tizimga olib kelinadi:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = \beta_1 + \alpha_{11}x_1 + \alpha_{12}x_2 + \alpha_{13}x_3 + \dots + \alpha_{1n}x_n \\ x_2 = \beta_2 + \alpha_{21}x_1 + \alpha_{22}x_2 + \alpha_{23}x_3 + \dots + \alpha_{2n}x_n \\ \dots \\ x_n = \beta_n + \alpha_{n1}x_1 + \alpha_{n2}x_2 + \alpha_{n3}x_3 + \dots + \alpha_{nn}x_n \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$\beta_i = \frac{b_i}{a_{ii}}; \quad \alpha_{ij} = -\frac{a_{ij}}{a_{ii}}; \quad a_{ii} \neq 0$$

Bu yerda

Bu yangi olingan tizimni qulaylik uchun matritsa ko'rinishida yozamiz

$$X = B + AX$$

Bu yerda - $X=\{x_i\}$, $B=\{\beta_i\}$ vektor; A diagonal elementlari nolga teng matritsa $A=\{\alpha_{ij}\}$

Bu tizimni ketma-ket yaqinlashish usuli bilan yechamiz. $B=\{\beta_j\}$ vektorini boshlang'ich nolinch qinlashish deb olib, $(k+1)$ yaqinlashish hisoblash formulasini quyidagicha yozamiz [3]

$$X^{(k+1)} = B + AX^{(k)} \quad (k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n).$$

Bu ketma-ket yaqinlashish $x^{(0)}, x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots, x^{(k)}$ limitga ega bo'lsa, u holda bu limit tizim yechimi bo'ladi. Iteratsiya usuli bo'yicha hisoblash oldindan berilgan aniqlik $\varepsilon > 0$ son uchun

$$|X^k - X^{k-1}| \leq \varepsilon$$

tengsizlik bajarilgunga qadar davom etadi. Iteratsiya jarayoni yaqinlashuvchi bo'lishi uchun A matritsaning

$$\|A\|_1 = \max_i \sum_{j=1}^n |\alpha_{ij}| < 1 \quad ; \quad \|A\|_2 = \max_j \sum_{i=1}^n |\alpha_{ij}| < 1 \quad ; \quad \|A\|_3 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^n |\alpha_{ij}|^2} < 1$$

formularidan birortasi bajarilishi yetarlidir [4].

Kramer usuli (Cramer's rule) chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasining yechimlarini determinantlar yordamida topishga asoslangan. Quyida C++ tilida n o'lchovli chiziqli tenglamalar sistemasini Kramer usulida yechish uchun dastur algoritmini tuzamiz [1].

Dastur algoritmi:

1. Matritsa determinantini hisoblash.
2. Har bir o'zgaruvchi uchun determinantlarni o'zgartirilgan matritsa yordamida hisoblash.
3. Kramer usuliga ko'ra o'zgaruvchilarning qiymatlarini topish.

Dastur uchta tenglama va uchta noma'lum uchun yozildi [6].

```
#include <iostream>
#include <vector>
using namespace std;
// Matritsa determinantini hisoblaydigan funksiya (3x3 matritsa uchun)
double determinant3x3(vector<vector<double>> mat) {
    double det = mat[0][0] * (mat[1][1] * mat[2][2] - mat[1][2] * mat[2][1])
        - mat[0][1] * (mat[1][0] * mat[2][2] - mat[1][2] * mat[2][0])
        + mat[0][2] * (mat[1][0] * mat[2][1] - mat[1][1] * mat[2][0]);
    return det;
}
// Kramer usuli bilan tenglamalar sistemasini yechish funksiyasi [2]
void kramerMethod(vector<vector<double>> A, vector<double> B) {
    // Asosiy matritsaning determinantini hisoblash
    double detA = determinant3x3(A);
    if (detA == 0) {
        cout << "Tizimning yechimi yo'q yoki cheksiz ko'p yechimga ega." << endl;
        return;
    }
    // X1 o'zgaruvchisi uchun determinantni hisoblash
```

```

vector<vector<double>> A1 = A;
for (int i = 0; i < 3; i++) {
    A1[i][0] = B[i]; // 1-ustunni B vektori bilan almashtiramiz
}
double detA1 = determinant3x3(A1);

// X2 o'zgaruvchisi uchun determinantni hisoblash
vector<vector<double>> A2 = A;
for (int i = 0; i < 3; i++) {
    A2[i][1] = B[i]; // 2-ustunni B vektori bilan almashtiramiz
}
double detA2 = determinant3x3(A2);
// X3 o'zgaruvchisi uchun determinantni hisoblash
vector<vector<double>> A3 = A;
for (int i = 0; i < 3; i++) {
    A3[i][2] = B[i]; // 3-ustunni B vektori bilan almashtiramiz
}
double detA3 = determinant3x3(A3);
// Kramer usuli bo'yicha yechimlarni hisoblash
double x1 = detA1 / detA;
double x2 = detA2 / detA;
double x3 = detA3 / detA;
// Yechimlarni ekranga chiqaramiz
cout << "Tenglamalar sistemasining yechimlari:" << endl;
cout << "x1 = " << x1 << endl;
cout << "x2 = " << x2 << endl;
cout << "x3 = " << x3 << endl;
}
int main() {
    // 3x3 matritsa (tenglamalar sistemasining koeffitsientlari)
    vector<vector<double>> A = {
        {2, -1, 3},
        {4, 1, 2},
        {3, 2, -4}
    };
    // B vektori (tenglamalarning o'ng tomoni)
    vector<double> B = {5, 9, -6};
    // Kramer usuli orqali yechishni chaqiramiz
    kramerMethod(A, B);
    return 0;}

```

- determinant3x3 funksiyasi 3x3 matritsaning determinantini hisoblaydi.

- kramerMethod funksiyasi Kramer usuliga ko'ra x_1 , x_2 va x_3 o'zgaruvchilarining qiymatlarini topadi.

Dasturdagi matritsa va vektorlarni xohlaganingizcha o'zgartirishingiz mumkin.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar/Используемая литература/References:

1. Shohamidov Sh. Amaliy matematika unsurlari. O'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent, "Fan va texnologiya", 2016, 212 b.
2. Raisov M. Matematik programmalash. Darslik. "Cho'lpon nomidagi" NMIU Tashkent: 2013, 208 b.
3. Xabibullayeva I. Iqtisodiy matematik usullar va modellar. O'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent, "Tafakkur bo'stoni", 2012, 112 b.
4. Isroilov M. Hisoblash usullari. Darslik. Toshkent, "Iqtisod-Moliya", 2008, 320 b
5. Mo'minov Sh. Matematik modellar va usullar. Darslik. Toshkent, "Turon-Istiqbol", 2006, 272 b.
6. Safoeva M. Matematik programmalash. O'quv qo'llanma. Toshkent, "UJBHT", 2004, 240 b.

INNOVATIVE
ACADEMY